

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for TGF-beta receptor type-2 (UniProt ID: P37173) for use in western blot and flow cytometry

Michael Biddle^{1*}, Jemma Cooper¹, Carolyn Jones², Katie Dixon¹, and Harvinder Virk^{1*}

¹College of Life Sciences, University of Leicester, LE1 7RH, United Kingdom

²Institute for Precision Health, University of Leicester, LE1 7RH, United Kingdom

*Corresponding authors: Michael Biddle (msb65@leicester.ac.uk) and Harvinder Virk (hsv6@leicester.ac.uk)

Abstract

Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis is a chronic, progressive interstitial lung disease characterised by excessive extracellular matrix deposition, leading to irreversible lung remodelling and respiratory failure. Transforming growth factor-beta 1 is a central driver of fibrogenesis, and its binding to transforming growth factor-beta receptor type 2 (TGFBR2) is essential for activation of both canonical and non-canonical signalling pathways. Given its critical role, TGFBR2 represents an important target for investigating disease pathogenesis and developing therapeutic strategies. However, the performance and specificity of commercially available antibodies targeting TGFBR2 have not been systematically evaluated, limiting reproducibility and confidence in experimental findings.

In this study, we systematically assessed eleven commercial antibodies by western blot and twelve by flow cytometry using a standardized knockout-based validation strategy in human A549 cells. Antibody performance was evaluated by comparing signals in TGFBR2 knockout cells with isogenic parental controls. These experiments are part of a broader collaborative effort to improve antibody reproducibility through the systematic characterization of commercial reagents and open dissemination of results. Although antibody performance may vary depending on experimental conditions, this work provides a practical resource to guide the selection of appropriate antibodies for studying TGFBR2 in health and disease.

Keywords

P37173, TGFBR2, TGF-beta receptor type-2, western blot, flow cytometry, idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis, IPF

Introduction

Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis is a chronic, progressive interstitial lung disease, characterised by excessive deposition of extracellular matrix proteins, leading to irreversible architectural distortion of the lung and ultimately respiratory failure (1). Among the key drivers of fibrogenesis, transforming growth factor-beta 1 (TGFB1) is widely recognised as a central mediator, promoting fibroblast activation, myofibroblast differentiation, and extracellular matrix production (2). To initiate this signalling cascade, TGFB1 binds to transforming growth factor-beta receptor type 2 (TGFBR2), which then recruits and phosphorylates transforming growth factor-beta receptor type 1 (TGFBR1), inducing SMAD2/3 phosphorylation (3).

As such, TGFBR2 represents an important target for understanding the molecular mechanisms underlying IPF and for the development of potential therapeutic strategies. However, the reliability of commercially available antibodies targeting TGFBR2 has not been systematically evaluated, limiting

the reproducibility and interpretability of experimental findings. Robust and well-validated antibodies are therefore essential to accurately detect TGFBR2 expression, localisation, and regulation across experimental systems.

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterising commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols (4) and openly sharing the data (5). Here we evaluated the performance of eleven commercial antibodies for TGFBR2 by western blot and twelve commercial antibodies by flow cytometry, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of TGFBR2 properties and function. The platform for antibody characterisation used to carry out this study was endorsed by a committee of industry and academic representatives. It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterisation procedures using most commercially available renewable antibodies against the corresponding protein. The standardised consensus antibody characterisation protocols are openly available on Protocols.io (DOI: [dx.doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)).

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterisation data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret the antibody characterisation data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (6).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from WT (wild type) and KO cells (7-9). The first step is to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcript per million "TPM" + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655). The A549 cell line expresses the *TGFBR2* transcript at $5.6 \log_2$ TPM+1, and a *TGFBR2* KO A549 cell line was obtained from Abcam (Table 1).

To screen TGFBR2 antibodies by western blot, protein lysates from both A549 WT and *TGFBR2* KO cell lines were run on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes and probed in parallel with eleven TGFBR2 antibodies (Figure 1).

For flow cytometry, A549 WT and *TGFBR2* KO cells were labelled with distinct fluorescent dyes and combined at a 1:1 ratio. Both cell lines were fixed, permeabilised and blocked in the same tube prior to antibody staining to reduce bias. Twelve TGFBR2 antibodies were then evaluated, with fluorescent intensity assessed using the Attune NxT flow cytometer. Antibody staining in both WT and KO line was then quantified using FlowJo software, with representative histograms presented in Figure 2.

In conclusion, we screened eleven commercial TGFBR2 antibodies by western blot and twelve by flow cytometry, comparing signals obtained from human A549 wild-type and *TGFBR2* knockout cells. High-quality, renewable antibodies capable of reliably detecting TGFBR2 were identified.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available TGFBR2 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners. We encourage readers to consult vendor documentation to identify the specific antigen each antibody is raised against, where such information is available.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in TGFBR2, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. TGFBR2 experts are invited to analyse and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots. Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Methods

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io (DOI: [dx.doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)).

Antibodies

All TGFBR2 antibodies are listed in Table 2, together with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRID), to ensure antibodies are cited properly (10). Secondary antibodies used in this study are provided in Table 3. To ensure consistency with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations (where antibody concentrations are not disclosed), antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios rather than absolute concentrations.

Cell culture

All cell lines used in this study are listed in Table 1, alongside their corresponding RRIDs, to ensure proper citation (11). Cells were cultured in DMEM (Capricorn Scientific #DMEM-HPSTA) supplemented

with 10% fetal bovine serum (Thermo Fisher Scientific #A5256801) and 1% antibiotic/antimycotic solution (Capricorn Scientific #AAS-B). All cell lines used in this study were routinely tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

Antibody screening by western blot

For lysate preparation, A549 WT and *TGFBR2* KO cells were washed three times in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific #70011044) and lysed in RIPA buffer containing 1x of protease inhibitor cocktail, sodium orthovanadate and phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride (Santa Cruz Biotechnology #sc-24948). Lysates were sonicated (40% amplitude for 5 seconds) three times and incubated for 30 minutes on ice prior to centrifugation at 20,000 x g for 1 hour at 4°C.

Protein concentration was confirmed using the Pierce BCA protein assay (Thermo Fisher Scientific #23225) and 30µg of protein was used. Samples were combined with Laemmli sample buffer (Bio-Rad #1610747) containing 2-mercaptoethanol (final concentration 355mM) (Sigma Aldrich #M7522) before being heated at 65°C for 10 minutes. Samples were then loaded in precast 4-20% WedgeWell Tris-Glycine Plus midi gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific #WTG42020BOX) alongside Prime-Step prestained broad range protein ladder (BioLegend #773302). SDS-PAGE was then performed in SureLock Tandem Midi Gel tanks (Thermo Fisher Scientific #STM1001) and run at 200V for 1 hour with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad #1610772). Proteins were then transferred to 0.2µm supported nitrocellulose membranes (Cytiva #10600015) using a Criterion blotter with plate electrodes (Bio-Rad #17004070) run at 85V for 45 minutes. Proteins on the blot were visualised with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific #161470250) which was scanned to show alongside individual western blots. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hour except for antibody 8697 which was blocked in 5% BSA in Tris-buffered saline containing 1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Thermo Fisher Scientific #J77500.K2). Primary antibodies were then incubated overnight at 4°C in 5% milk TBST with gentle shaking. Following three ten-minute washes with TBST, horseradish peroxidase (HRP) conjugated secondary antibodies were incubated at a dilution of 1/10000 (0.1µg/mL) in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hour at room temperature followed by three ten-minute washes with TBST. Membranes were then incubated with either Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific #32106) for 1 minute or Clarity Western ECL substrate (Bio-Rad #1705061) for 5 minutes prior to detection with the ImageQuant LAS 4000.

Antibody screening by flow cytometry: intracellular staining

A549 WT and *TGFBR2* KO cells were detached, and seven million cells were labelled with CellTracker green or violet, fluorescent dyes, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, #C7025 and #C10094). WT and KO cells were centrifuged at 300 x g, for 10 minutes and resuspended in PBS containing 1% bovine serum albumin (BSA) (Sigma-Aldrich, A9647). The two populations were combined at a 1:1 ratio, centrifuged and fixed on ice for 20 minutes using 800 µL of 4% PFA in PBS (Thermo Fisher Scientific #J19943.K2). Following fixation, 1.2 mL of 1% BSA in PBS was added to the tube, vortexed and centrifuged at 600 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C. Cells were then permeabilised in 400 µL PBS with 0.1% Saponin (Sigma-Aldrich #558255) for 10 minutes at room temperature, centrifuged at 600 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C and then blocked with 5% goat serum (Sigma-Aldrich #G6767), 1% BSA, 0.1% saponin in PBS for 30 minutes on ice. After the blocking step 400,000 cells were aliquoted into individually labelled tubes, centrifuged at 600 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C and incubated in 150µL of 1% BSA, 0.1% Saponin PBS with primary *TGFBR2* antibodies for 30 minutes on ice. 500µL of 1% BSA, 0.1% saponin PBS was then added to each tube, vortexed and centrifuged at 600 x g for 15 minutes at 4°C. Cells were then incubated with their corresponding Multi-rAb CoraLite® Plus 647 secondary antibodies (Table 3) in 150 µL of 1% BSA, 0.1% saponin PBS for 30 minutes on ice. For conjugated antibodies the addition of a secondary antibody was excluded and replaced with 150 µL of 1% BSA, 0.1% saponin in

PBS during this incubation. 500 μ l of 1% BSA, 0.1% saponin PBS was then added to each tube, vortexed and centrifuged 600 \times *g* for 15 minutes at 4°C.

Tubes were then resuspended in 1 ml of 1% BSA in PBS and data was acquired using the Attune NxT flow cytometer. Data was analysed using FlowJo with the following gates. The cell population was first gated on FSC-A vs SSC-A, within that gate single cells were selected by FSC-A vs FSC-H and then KO and WT cells were isolated by BL1-A vs VL1-A using a quadrat gate. Quantification of antibody staining was then observed in the RL1-A channel and histograms merged to demonstrate the staining intensity between the two populations compared to the two secondary only controls. The figure was then assembled using Adobe Illustrator 2024.

Antibody screening by flow cytometry: cell surface staining

For cell surface staining A549 WT and *TGFBR2* KO cells were detached, and seven million cells were labelled with CellTracker green or violet, fluorescent dyes, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, #C7025 and #C10094). WT and KO cells were centrifuged at 400 \times *g*, for 10 minutes and resuspended in PBS containing 1% bovine serum albumin (BSA) (Sigma-Aldrich, A9647). Cell populations were then combined at a 1:1 ratio, centrifuged and blocked on ice for 30 min with with 5% goat serum (Sigma Aldrich #G6767), 1% BSA in PBS. After the blocking step 400,000 cells were aliquoted into individually labelled tubes, centrifuged at 400 \times *g* for 15 minutes at 4°C, and incubated in 150 μ L of 1% BSA PBS with primary TGFBR2 antibodies for 30 minutes on ice. 500 μ L of 1% BSA PBS was then added to each tube, vortexed gently and centrifuged at 400 \times *g* for 15 minutes at 4°C. Cells were then incubated for 30 minutes on ice with their corresponding Multi-rAb CoraLite[®] Plus 647 secondary antibodies (Table 3) in 150 μ l of 1% BSA, PBS. For conjugated antibodies the addition of a secondary antibody was excluded and replaced with 150 μ L of 1% BSA PBS during this incubation. 500 μ L of 1% BSA PBS was then added to each tube, gently vortexed and centrifuged at 400 \times *g* for 15 minutes at 4°C. Tubes were then resuspended in 1 mL of 1% BSA PBS with 1 μ L of sytox orange (Thermo Fisher, S34861) and incubated on ice for 20 minutes. Data was then acquired using the Attune NxT flow cytometer.

Data was analysed using FlowJo with the following gates. The cell population was first gated on FSC-A vs SSC-A, and single cells were then selected by FSC-A vs FSC-H. Viable cells were identified by gating the sytox orange negative population using YL1-A vs SCC-A and within that gate, KO and WT cells were isolated by BL1-A vs VL1-A using a quadrat gate. Quantification of antibody staining was then observed in the RL1-A channel and histograms merged to demonstrate the staining intensity between the two populations. The figure was then assembled using Adobe Illustrator 2024.

Data availability

Underlying data

Zenodo: Dataset for the TGFBR2 antibody screening study <DOI>

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

Grant information

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The funders have no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Addgene, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, Institute for Protein Innovation, MilliporeSigma, Miltenyi Biotec, Proteintech, Synaptic Systems, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1. Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalogue number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Abcam	AB288558	CVCL_0023	A549	WT
Abcam	AB261863	CVCL_B2QI	A549	TGFBR2 KO

Table 2. Summary of the TGFBR2 antibodies tested.

Company	Catalogue number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Stock concentration (µg/mL)	Vendor recommended applications
Abcam	ab184948**	1062725-6	AB_2818975	Monoclonal Recombinant	EPR14673	Rabbit	2326	WB
Abcam	ab259360**	1001702-24	AB_3668832	Monoclonal Recombinant	EPR24349-124	Rabbit	469	IP, WB
Abcam	ab270440**	1025845-8	-	Monoclonal Recombinant	EPR23237-2	Rabbit	584	FC, ICC/IF
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP44743_T100	QC14853-20071108	AB_938452	Polyclonal	-	Rabbit	1000	WB
Cell Signalling Technology	41896S**	2	AB_3668871	Monoclonal Recombinant	E5M6F	Rabbit	340	WB
GeneTex	GTX129909	41836	AB_2886121	Polyclonal	-	Rabbit	360	WB
Miltenyi Biotec	130-115-067**	5250201912	AB_2726890	Monoclonal Recombinant	REA903	Human	-	FC-CS, ICC/IF, IHC
ProteinTech	66636-1-Ig*	10023257	AB_2881995	Monoclonal	2D5H7	Mouse	1000	ELISA, IHC, WB
R & D Systems	MAB2411*	ITL0324051	AB_2202474	Monoclonal	176510	Mouse	500	WB
Thermo Fisher Scientific	701683**	2827651	AB_2608868	Monoclonal Recombinant	16H2L4	Rabbit	500	ICC/IF, WB
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-51441**	ZJ4521736A	AB_3093813	Monoclonal Recombinant	8A3Q9	Rabbit	203	IHC
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-55343**	ZJ4521730	AB_3667584	Monoclonal Recombinant	2M8Y2	Rabbit	2000	WB

* Monoclonal antibody, ** Recombinant antibody.

ELISA = Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay, FC = Flow cytometry, FC-CS = Flow cytometry (cell surface), ICC/IF = Immunocytochemistry/immunofluorescence, IHC = immunohistochemistry, IP = immunoprecipitation, WB = Western blot.

Table 3. Summary of the secondary antibodies used.

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalogue number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Application	Stock concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	Working concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	Recombinant Polyclonal	Western blot	1000	0.1
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Mouse (H+L)	RGAM001	AB_3068333	Recombinant Polyclonal	Western blot	1000	0.1
Proteintech	Coralite-Plus-647-Goat Anti-Rabbit (H + L)	RGAR005	AB_3073509	Recombinant Polyclonal	Flow cytometry	500	0.625
Proteintech	Coralite-Plus-647-Goat Anti-Mouse (H + L)	RGAM005	AB_3073503	Recombinant Polyclonal	Flow cytometry	500	0.625

Figure 1: TGF-beta receptor type-2 antibody screening by immunoblot

Figure 2: TGF-beta receptor type-2 antibody screening by flow cytometry (PFA/ Saponin)

Figure 3: TGF-beta receptor type-2 antibody screening by flow cytometry (cell surface)

Figure legends

Figure 1: TGFBR2 antibody screening by western blot using protein lysates

Protein lysates from A549 WT and *TGFBR2* KO cells were collected, and 30µg of protein was used for western blot with the indicated TGFBR2 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO samples. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab184948** at 1/1000, ab259360** at 1/1000, ab270440** at 1/500, ARP44743_T100 at 1/500, 41896S** at 1/1000, GTX129909 at 1/1000, 66636-1-Ig* at 1/1000, MAB2411* at 1/500, 701683** at 1/500, MA5-51441** at 1/1000, MA5-55343** at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 64.6kDa. ** = recombinant antibody, * = monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: TGFBR2 antibody screening by flow cytometry: intracellular staining

A549 WT and *TGFBR2* KO cells were labelled with a green or violet, fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed in a 1:1 ratio, fixed in 4% PFA and permeabilized in 0.1% saponin. 400,000 cells were stained with the indicated TGFBR2 antibodies and corresponding Multi-rAb CoraLite® Plus 647 secondary antibodies (except 130-115-067 which was conjugated). Antibody staining was quantified using the Attune NxT Flow Cytometer with representative images showing the staining intensity in the KO population (pink histogram, dashed line) compared to the WT cells (green histogram, solid line). For unconjugated antibodies grey histograms with dotted lines represent secondary antibody-only controls in both WT and KO cells. For conjugated antibodies blue histograms with dotted lines represent fluorescence minus one control in both WT and KO cells. ab184948** at 1/2326, ab259360** at 1/469, ab270440** at 1/584, ARP44743_T100 at 1/1000, 41896S** at 1/340, GTX129909 at 1/360, 130-115-067** at 1/1000, 66636-1-Ig* at 1/1000, MAB2411* at 1/500, 701683** at 1/500, MA5-51441** at 1/203, MA5-55343** at 1/2000. ** = recombinant antibody, * = monoclonal antibody.

Figure 3: TGFBR2 antibody screening by flow cytometry: cell surface

A549 WT and *TGFBR2* KO cells were labelled with a green or violet, fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed in a 1:1 ratio, and 400,000 cells were stained with the indicated TGFBR2 antibodies. Multi-rAb CoraLite® Plus 647 secondary antibodies were then added except for 130-115-067 which was conjugated. Antibody staining was quantified using the Attune NxT Flow Cytometer with representative images showing the staining intensity in the KO population (pink histogram, dashed line) compared to the WT cells (green histogram, solid line). For unconjugated antibodies grey histograms with dotted lines represent secondary antibody-only controls in both WT and KO cells. For conjugated antibodies blue histograms with dotted lines represent fluorescence minus one control in both WT and KO cells. ab184948** at 1/2326, ab259360** at 1/469, ab270440** at 1/584, ARP44743_T100 at 1/1000, 41896S** at 1/340, GTX129909 at 1/360, 130-115-067** at 1/100, 66636-1-Ig* at 1/1000, MAB2411* at 1/500, 701683** at 1/500, MA5-51441** at 1/203, MA5-55343** at 1/2000. ** = recombinant antibody, * = monoclonal antibody.